

COMPOSITE PROPELLER SHAFTS DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION

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Design parameters for composite propeller shaft tubes are discussed and a method for computerized optimization is developed taking into account a multi variant approach based on design criteria and material properties.

INTRODUCTION

Vehicle components from composite materials result in considerable weight savings and also in reduction of total energy requirements for production of parts [1,2]. Since about five years many groups are active in this field and propeller shafts are the main components worked on in several countries. Besides potential weight reduction and energy savings mentioned, other reasons for these developments are the possibility of noise and vibration damping [3], prevention of metallic corrosion and the chance of using one-piece composite shafts instead of two piece steel or aluminium propeller shafts.

Despite such advantages no real mass production will be on stream within next year and only few companies have announced their commitment for a future large scale production. The reason is that for any vehicle model the composite propeller shaft must be adapted to the specific constraints given and that vehicle engineers have to take into consideration the new properties of composite propeller shafts in designing gears, bearings, joints, etc. for new cars or trucks. So very close cooperation between car manufacturer and composite part producer is necessary. In optimizing composite propeller shaft tubes therefore all the "outside" constraints from the vehicle have to be considered as the end-fitting technique, the service temperature range. Mass production technology and quality control methods are also to be developed.

PROPELLER SHAFT DESIGN

Table 1 shows that besides geometrical conditions the mechanical main requirements are the torsional moment and the critical shaft rotation speed. The thermal demands are very important for calculating thermal stresses always present and for selecting the optimum matrix system for a given case. Matrix selection is more difficult than usually stated if matrix-fibre interaction under dynamic load at elevated temperatures has to be taken into consideration -wich is the case for propellershafts for cars especially-.

PROPELLER SHAFT DESIGN CRITERIA

<u>geometrical requirements</u>
- length
- diameter (max. outside diameter)
- fitting design
<u>mechanical requirements</u>
- critical rotation speed (rpm)
- torsional moment
..... max. torque
..... load history
- torsional stiffness
..... γ_{min}
..... γ_{max}
- damping characteristics
..... longitudinal
..... torsional
<u>thermal requirements</u>
- max. temperatur of component in service
- min. temperatur of component in service

TABLE 1 Propeller shaft design criteria

CRITICAL LENGTH

The equation for the first critical frequency of a simply supported thin rotating tube

$$n_{crit} = \frac{15 \cdot \pi}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{d_m}{L^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{\rho}} \quad (n: [RPM]) \quad (1)$$

d_m = mean diameter [mm] , L = length [mm] ,

E = youngs modulus [N/mm^2], ρ = density [g/mm^3]

shows that the critical rotating speed is dependent on

- the specific modulus of elasticity (for orthotropic material the modulus in longitudinal direction of the shaft E_x) and
- the geometry of the propeller shaft with the ratio d_m/L^2

For a required critical rotating speed $n_{crit, requ.}$, a given mean diameter d_m and the material dependent specific modulus E/ρ the critical length L_{crit} is

$$L_{crit} = \sqrt{\frac{15 \cdot \pi}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{d_m}{n_{crit}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{\rho}}} \quad (n: [RPM]) \quad (2)$$

and for a given length the minimum required mean diameter $d_{m, requ.}$ is

$$d_{m, requ} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot L^2 \cdot n_{crit, requ}}{15 \cdot \pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{\rho}}} \quad (n: [RPM]) \quad (3)$$

In fig. 2 the critical shaft length and the minimum required diameter are plotted for different material parameters for a critical rotating speed of 7 200 RPM. Besides steel and aluminium different FRP shafts calculated with standard values for glass-, aramid (Kevlar RTM type) and two different carbon fibre types are considered, see also fig. 1. For all FRP types the highest modulus of elasticity in longitudinal direction of the shaft is realized if the fibres are in longitudinal direction ($\omega = 0^\circ$). As the shear strength of a shaft with 0° -fibre orientation is comparatively low, fig 2 is based on a realistic fibre orientation of $\omega = \pm 15^\circ$.

Although the critical shaft length is only a function of the fourth root of the specific modulus -Eq. (2)-practical applications show stupendous limits and possibilities for the different materials.

Most cars have propeller shafts within about 1 250 mm and 1 750 mm of length. Assuming a limiting diameter of 70 mm it is striking that the critical length of propeller shafts from steel, aluminium or glass-FRP is just at the lower limit of this range. Therefore in these cases the usual two piece propeller shaft (fig.3) is the only solution to avoid vibrations. In contrast to this FRP types can be found to realize one piece propeller shafts, fig. 3b. The elimination of the middle bearing and additional yokes leads to a further weight and cost reduction.

Similar considerations see fig. 2 can be made for light and heavy trucks, where often larger diameters are possible and where the substitution of a two-piece propeller shaft by a one-piece propeller shaft or of a three-piece propeller shaft by a one or two-piece propeller shaft using FRP can be realized. Most interesting are medium diameters and lengths, e. g. $d_m = 70$ mm and $l = 1\ 500$ mm. Here different solutions are possible, e. g. all aramid type, all carbon type or several hybrid types.

For optimal fibre combination, with respect to weight and costs, besides the critical rotating speed a strength analysis must be done which for a given torque and a distinct margin of safety leads to a material dependent wall thickness.

ELASTIC AND STRENGTH BEHAVIOR OF FRP

FRP, as discussed here, is a multi-layer composite consisting of a defined number of unidirectional reinforced single layers with different fibre orientations, fig. 4. Multi-layer analysis has been discussed in many papers [4 to 10]. So only some aspects have to be discussed. With the methods of the multi-layer analysis mentioned, the elastic behavior of any defined combination of layers can be calculated from the elastic behavior of the unidirectional (UD) reinforced single layer as it was done for some two layer cross ply composites in fig. 1. (The elastic behavior of UD layers is defined by the modulus parallel and perpendicular to the fibres one of the two poisson's ratios, and the in-plane shear modulus - fig. 6a).

In every multi-layer laminate under uniform or combined stress each single layer generally is under combined stress (fig. 4).

For determining the margin of safety the actual stress state of each single layer has to be compared with the failure body for the unidirectional basic element, fig. 5. The failure body for unidirectional fibre/matrix (E/m) composites consists of two surfaces, one for fibre failure and one for inter-fibre failure (cohesive failure within the matrix or adhesiv failure at the interface) [5].

Multi-layer analysis, computer aided laminate design and the optimization of the fibre orientation, also for non-linear stress-strain behavior, can be considered as state of the art. Therefore with the increasing number of commercially available types of reinforcing fibers the main task is the compilation of the basic mechanical data.

In addition to the rod specimen for the measurement of the properties in fibre direction, fig. 6c, the tubular hoopwound test specimen (fig. 6b) allows measurement of all other mechanical properties needed for a complete description of an orthotropic material. Besides the properties parallel to the fibres the properties transverse to the fibre axis and the behavior under shear are even more important in composite design.

Very important is the determination of the failure curve for combined normal stress perpendicular to the fibers and the inplane shear stress (see curve I in fig. 5). The test machine is made to load the tubular specimen either by uniform or combined tension, compression and torsion, fig. 7. The failure curve I in fig. 5 is determined by a series of tests under combined loading with well-defined ratios of tension/torsion or of compression/torsion.

It is well known that for different fibre types and applications with different temperature needs different matrix resins are required; systematic test series and basic data documentations are indispensable to find the optimal fibre/matrix combination.

OPTIMIZATION OF FRP PROPELLER SHAFTS

Given geometric conditions and a defined required rotating speed deliver a first selection of suitable fibre/matrix (f/m) systems. In order to select the best out of the available f/m systems and in order to determine the optimal fibre orientation, the torsional strength, buckling and stiffness have to be calculated in an iterative process.

Fig. 9 shows the flow chart of an optimization program for a two-f/m-system hybrid propeller shaft. For any combination of two of the available f/m systems and their mechanical properties (loop I) and within a limited diameter (loop II) the fibre orientation angles ω_1 and ω_2 are varied (loop III).

For each pair of ω_1 and ω_2 , depending on a required critical rotating speed a defined ratio for the two fibre parts can be found. The minimum required wall thickness is available through strength and stiffness analysis and gives together with the above calculated thickness ratio the weight and cost of the example discussed.

Systematic variation of the fibre angles, the f/m systems and the shaft diameter results in optimum designs for minimum weight, for minimum cost or for minimum cost at limited weight.

The approach described enables the designer to find for each case the optimum propeller shaft design (fig. 10).

Design and optimization of composite propeller shaft-tubes must be discussed in the context of a given mass production technology. We have found that a specifically adapted and optimized reciprocal filament winding process in contrast to continuous filament winding is suitable for large scale production of propeller shaft-tubes. This is due to the high production speed and flexibility achieved and the precision of components required. Other groups got similar results favouring filament winding over pultrusion, tape wrap and tape roll techniques [2]. So, today cycle times between 1-5 minutes per shaft-tube can be envisaged.

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Fig.1 : Standard values for the specific modulus E_x/ρ of four FRP cross-ply laminates with varied fibre angle and of steel and aluminium.

Fig. 2 : Critical length and required mean diameter of different one piece FRP propeller shafts and propeller shafts from steel and aluminium for a critical rotating speed of 7 200 RPM.

TWO PIECE STEEL PROP SHAFT

ONE PIECE FRP PROP SHAFT

Fig. 3 : Usual two piece steel propeller shaft and one piece FRP shaft.

Fig. 4 : Multi layer composite and unidirectional single layer (schematic).
Stresses in global coordinates and in fibre oriented coordinates.

UD - ELEMENT

FAILURE BODY

Fig. 5 : Failure body for unidirectional (UD) composite [6]

Fig. 6 : a) unidirectional (UD) composite element

b) tubular hoop-wound test specimen

c) rod test specimen

Fig. 7 Servo hydraulic test machine for tubular specimens.
Loading conditions: tension, compression, torsion and combinations.
Foto: CIBA-GEIGY AG, Basle (CH)

COMPOSITE PROPELLER SHAFT

Fig. 8 : Scheme of composite propeller shaft, consisting of two fibre types in four fibre directions (two cross-ply arrangement)

Fig. 9 : Flow chart for optimization of FRP propeller shafts

Fig. 10

Examples of composite propeller shafts for different requirements ; from top to bottom :

- all carbon/epoxy (2 x)
- all aramid/epoxy
- glass/carbon/epoxy - interply hybrid
- glass/carbon/epoxy - intraply hybrid
- all glass/epoxy

Foto : CIBA-GEIGY AG, Basle (CH)